

THE ROLE OF THE EDUCATION SYSTEM IN THE RENAISSANCE OF DURING THE PERIOD OF AMIR TIMUR AND TIMURIDS

Mavlanov U.M.

*Doctor of historical sciences, Professor,
National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek.*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11122672>

It is recognized all over the world that the current territory of Uzbekistan is the “heart” of Central Asia, which is considered one of the ancient centers of world civilization. The formation and gradual development of the regional civilization was directly related to the activity of the educational system. It is known that elementary schools and adult education centers were formed in the ancient Turan region from ancient times. The main centers of learning, as in all regions of the world, are thought to have been mainly under the temples. Not only religious education and upbringing, but also worldly knowledge was given in the synagogues, the children of the population, first of all the upper classes, were educated.

In the “Beishi” from ancient Chinese sources, there is information that in the early Middle Ages, the Sugdians sent a boy to school from the age of 5 and taught him to read and write [1]. These and other data show that the educational system and the literacy level of the population in our region were high for their time.

Beruni reports that Qutayba killed all the literate people in Khorezm, burned the books in the temples, and the population became illiterate [2]. This information is twofold. First of all, it shows that before the Arab invasion, the education system, science and cultural-educational development in Central Asia were high, and the educational centers were under the temples. Secondly, after the Arab invasion, the children of the local population, who became illiterate for a certain period of time, took a leading place in the creation of the Islamic renaissance period by mastering the Arabic language. They made a great contribution to spreading the ideas of Islam's call to knowledge and morals and enlightenment in the Islamic world and throughout the world. This also shows that the pursuit of knowledge and enlightenment was an ancient value among the ancient Turanian peoples.

In the early Islamic period, primary schools and madrasahs began to be established in Movarounnahr. The fact that our great ancestors received their initial education in the large cities of Movarounnahr and Khorezm, which are known as the cultural and scientific centers of the Islamic world, is a clear evidence of the achievements of the educational system during this period. Movarounnahr became one of the cultural centers of the Islamic world in the 9th-12th centuries, which is recognized as the first Islamic renaissance period. The scientific heritage left by our

great ancestors who lived in this period set the standards of the culture of the Islamic era and had a great impact on the development of the civilization of all mankind [3].

During the rule of Amir Temur and the Timurids, attention to education and patronage of science became a state policy in Movarunnahr and Khorasan. Madrasahs were established in all cities, and mature scientists and scholars of their time were attracted to teach science. The era of Amir Temur and the Timurids is significant as a period of highly developed education and science in the ancient Turan region. The development of the renaissance of the Timurid period was directly influenced by the establishment of a fair administration system in the vast kingdom founded by Amir Temur [4]. Amir Temur relied on ancient Turkish traditions of statehood and Islamic sharia to build a powerful kingdom and an enlightened society. He deeply understood that the basis of any progress is a quality education system. For this reason, Sahibgiron, first of all, followed the path of establishing education and upbringing in the right way, raising the position of knowledgeable and enlightened persons in the society. Many primary schools were established in all cities and large villages of the vast kingdom. According to historical sources, during this period, the tradition of sending a boy to school when he was 4 years, 4 months and 4 days old was practiced, and primary education covered all the cultural lands of the vast kingdom [5].

As was the case throughout the Islamic era, in this period as well, madrasah education played a key role in the development of science in the country, and many madrasahs with higher education centers were built in large cities, which were the cultural centers of the Sultanate. Attention to education, patronage of science was raised to the level of state policy during the period of Amir Temur and the Timurids. The task of the owner to the administrators of the kingdom is also reflected in the "Temur Tuzuklari" as *"Let them build mosques, madrasahs and khanaqahs in every city, big and small"*; *"Let them determine the daily salaries of Mudarris and sheikhs"*; *"May the Sayyids, Ulama, Mashayikh, Fuzalo, Ulug be held dear"*. This task of the owner was naturally carried out within the whole kingdom. *"I appointed scholars and mudarris in every city to teach Muslims about religious issues and to teach them about Shari'a beliefs and Islamic religious knowledge, such as tafsir, hadith, and fiqh"*; *"I considered the Sayyids, scholars, mashoyikhs, intellectuals, muhaddiths, historians to be good and considerate people, and honoured them"*, says Sahibqiran in his Tuzuk [6].

By the order of Amir Temur, religious sciences (exegesis, hadith studies, jurisprudence, etc.) as well as secular sciences (geometry, algebra, arithmetic, mathematics, logic, astronomy, astrology, literature, history, astrology, etc.) were widely taught in madrasahs. The large-scale creative work carried out in the country

created a great need for high-level specialists in specific sciences, in particular, mathematics, geometry, architecture, and engineering. Madrasahs, which are higher education institutions in the Turanian country, performed the role of large scientific centers and centers of enlightenment during the era of Amir Temur and the Timurids. Each madrasah in the cities was allocated endowment land, and the income from them was sufficient for the salaries of madrasahs and employees, library maintenance, repairs and other works [7].

Amir Temur was invited to teach in the madrasahs of the country of Turan by famous scientists and scholars of the Islamic world. By order of Amir Temur, a unique library of its time was established in Samarkand, during the reign of Mirza Ulughbek (1409-1449), the fund of this library was further enriched and became a real center of knowledge and enlightenment of the country.

It is recorded in historical sources that Sahibqiran, who highly valued knowledge, consulted with scholars. In particular, Sharofiddin Ali Yazdi notes in the work "Zafarnoma" that when Amir Temur wanted to solve a problem, he first consulted with knowledgeable experts and scientists in this field. Amir Temur respected historians and scientists very much, and by order of Sahibqiron, the work of engravers and historians was established in the palace[8]. This led to the high development of historiography during the period of Amir Temur and the Timurids.

It is known from the history of the world that the development of science requires large investments and state patronage. As the enlightened ruler Amir Temur deeply understood this, he raised the patronage of people of knowledge and creativity to the level of state policy in all regions of the huge kingdom. In modern terms, "state grants" were allocated to various fields of science, famous scientists and scholars, and their scientific activities were financed from the state treasury. As a result of this policy, the intellectual potential of the Islamic world began to flow to Samarkand, the capital of Turan, and other cities. Scientists have become an influential social stratum of society. All conditions were created for them to live and engage in scientific activities.

The creativity of scientists and scholars who came to Samarkand from different regions of the great kingdom, their scientific activities in various fields of science played a key role in the creation of a new renaissance period in the ancient Turan land.

Amir Temur's patronage policy for science was carried out by his successors, in particular Mirza Ulughbek. Although Mirza Ulughbek was born in a distant Sultanate, he was brought up in the capital of the Sultanate, Samarkand, and received his first education in this city, which became an influential center of science and enlightenment of the entire Islamic world with the efforts of his grandfather Amir

Temur. Mirza Ulughbek (1409-1449) paid great attention to the establishment of madrasas, which became major educational centers of the Islamic world, and to attract mature scholars and scholars of his time to teach in these madrasas. In this respect, Mirza Ulughbek occupies a special place among Timurid rulers.

During the reign of Mirza Ulughbek, an observatory was built in Samarkand, madrasas were built in Bukhara, Gijduvan and Samarkand. During this period, more than 100 scientists achieved great achievements in various fields of science in the city of Samarkand alone. Among them were Taftazani, Maulana Ahmed, Qazizada Rumi, known as "Plato" of his time, Ghiyasiddin Koshi, Muhammad Hafavi, Maulana Ali Kushchi and other famous people. On the initiative of Qazizada Rumi (Bursa 1360 - Samarkand 1437), who came to Samarkand in 1410 and was a teacher at the Ulughbek madrasa, which started work in 1420, later Ghiyosiddin Jamshid al-Koshi and other famous scholars were invited to Samarkand. About 60 scientists worked in different fields of science at the Ulughbek madrasa in Samarkand. Honored by his contemporaries as the "Plato of the Age", Qazizada Rumi taught mathematics and astronomy at the madrasa and served as the head of the observatory after the death of Ghiyaziddin Jamshid. Qazizada Rumi also led the construction of the Ulughbek observatory in Samarkand, and participated in the compilation of the star chart in Ulughbek's work "Zizhi Kurogoni" [9].

In this way, scholars became a social stratum with great respect and status in Amir Temur and the Timurid kingdom, which gave rise to the Second Islamic Renaissance in Movarunnahr and Khorasan. It led to the transformation of Samarkand, Kesh, Bukhara, Khivot and other cities into centers of enlightenment and science. International trade and cultural relations were restored along the Great Silk Road, cooperation in various fields of science was established, and diplomatic relations were established with neighboring and distant countries [10]. At the heart of these changes, the state policy focused on science, culture and art, and education, which was founded by Amir Temur and continued by many Timurid rulers, was of great importance.

During the reigns of Shahrukh (1405-1447), Mirza Ulughbek (1409-1449), Sultan Abu Said (1451-1469), Sultan Husain (Boyqara) (1469-1506), science and culture flourished, and Movarounnahr and Khurasan became famous as major cultural centers of the Islamic world.

It is known that Alisher Navoi continued the traditions founded by Sahibqiran by sponsoring many representatives of science, art and literature of his time. In particular, the patronage of Alisher Navoi played an important role in the creative activities of Kamoliddin Behzod, Sultan Ali Mashhadi, Husayn Uddiy, Kamoliddin

Binai, Davlatshah Samarkandi, Husayn Voiz Koshifiy, Mirkhand, Zayniddin Vasifiy and others [11].

The majestic architectural structures built during the reign of Amir Temur and the Timurids clearly demonstrate the power of the country and the great rise based on creativity. On the direct initiative of the owner, cities such as Samarkand, Bukhara, Termiz, Marv, Binokat, which were destroyed during the Mongol invasion, were restored, and many new towns and villages were built. The architectural complex of the Ak-Sarai (White Palace) in Shahrisabz, glorified as "Qubbat ul-adab wal-ilm", Bibi Khanim Mosque in Samarkand, Gor Amir's mausoleum, Shahizinda architectural complex, Zangi Ota near Tashkent, Ahmad Yassavi's mausoleum in Turkestan and other buildings are majestic structures built during the reign of Amir Temur, they are making a great contribution to the development of tourism in our country today.

Адабиётлар:

1. Бичурин Н.Я (Иакинф). Собрание сведений о народах, обитавших в Средней Азии в древние времена. В 3-х частях. – Алматы: ТОО “Жалын Баспасы”, 1998. Ч.2. – С. 157.

2. Абу Райхон Беруний. Қадимги халқлардан қолган ёдгорликлар (Осор ал-боқия). – Тошкент: O'zbekiston, 2022. I том. – Б. 74.

3. Сулаймонова Ф. Шарқ ва Ғарб (Қадимги давр ва ўрта асрлар маданий алоқалари). – Ташкент: Ўзбекистон, 1991. – 160 б.

4. Сағдуллаев А., Мавлонов Ў. Ўзбекистонда давлат бошқаруви тарихи. – Тошкент: Академия, 2006. – 140 б.

5. Мирза Мухаммад Хайдар. Та'рих-и Рашиди/ Введение, перевод с персидского А. Урунбаева, Р.П. Джалиловой, Л.М. Епифановой. Примечание и указатели Р.П.Джалиловой и Л.М.Епифановой. – Ташкент: Фан, 1996. – С. 252.

6. Темур тузуклари // Форсчадан А. Соғуний ва Ҳ.Кароматов тарж. – Тошкент: Гофур Гулом, 1996. – Б. 73.

7. Темур ва Улуғбек даври тарихи. Муаллифлар жамоаси. Бош муҳаррир А. Асқаров. – Тошкент: Қомуслар бош таҳририяти, 1996.

8. Шарафуддин Али Йаздий. Зафарнома / Мухаммад Али ибн Дарвиш Али ал-Бухорий таржимаси. Сўз боши, табдил, изоҳлар ва кўрсаткичлар муаллифлари А. Аҳмад ва Ҳ. Бобобеков. – Тошкент: Шарқ, 1997. – 384 б.

9. Бартольд В.В. Улугбек и его время //Работы по отдельным проблемам истории Средней Азии. II. часть 1. – Москва: Наука, 1964. - С. 63-175.

10. Мавлонов Ў.М. Марказий Осиёнинг қадимги йўллари: шаклланиши ва ривожланиш босқичлари. – Тошкент: Akademiya, 2008. - Б. 180-185.

11. Гиёсиддин ибн Хумомиддин Хондамир. Ҳабиб ус-сияр фи ахбори афроди башар (Башар аҳли сийратидан хабар берувчи дўст). – Тошкент: O'zbekiston, 2013. - Б. 787-794.